

SOCIAL INFLUENCE, CONSPICUOUS CONSUMPTION, AND REPURCHASE INTENTIONS: EXPLORING THE ROLE OF BEHAVIORAL FACTORS IN FUNCTIONAL FOOD CONSUMPTION

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Abstract

This study explores the relationship between conspicuous consumption behavior and functional food consumption, shedding light on an area of research that is still relatively uncommon. The findings reveal that conspicuous consumption behavior extends beyond tangible luxury goods to include functional foods, influencing consumers' perceptions of social status. Of the seven hypotheses tested, four were confirmed, demonstrating the impact of social influence, attitude toward functional food, and customer satisfaction on repurchase intention. Social influence was found to positively influence both conspicuous consumption behavior and attitudes toward functional food, aligning with theories of conspicuous consumption and social influence. Contrary to expectations, health consciousness did not significantly affect functional food consumption, suggesting that consumers may not fully recognize the social status implications of functional food consumption. Additionally, while customer satisfaction was found to positively influence repurchase intention, conspicuous consumption behavior did not directly impact repurchase intention, suggesting that other factors may mediate this relationship. Overall, these findings contribute to our understanding of conspicuous consumption in the context of functional foods, highlighting the importance of social influence and customer satisfaction in driving consumer behavior. This research offers insights for businesses and practitioners in the functional food industry, suggesting the importance of incorporating social contexts into marketing campaigns to appeal to consumers' conspicuous consumption behavior. Additionally, while health consciousness plays a role in consumer behavior, companies may prioritize social influence in their messaging. Finally, to encourage repurchase intention, companies must prioritize customer satisfaction, although further research is needed to identify additional factors influencing satisfaction in the functional foods industries

Keyword: Conspicuous Consumption, Functional Food, Social Influence, Health Consciousness, Attitude, Customer Satisfaction, Repurchase Intention.

1. INTRODUCTION

Conspicuous consumption is defined as possessing and displaying luxury products and activities to improve social positioning. This term was introduced by American economist and sociologist Thorstein Veblen in 1899. Conspicuous consumption can also serve as a form of social comparison, where individuals measure their success and status relative to others based on material possessions. In this way, consumption becomes not just about fulfilling needs, but about asserting one's place in the social hierarchy.

Conspicuous consumption manifests in various areas of life, such as luxury goods, leisure and recreation, education, social events such as weddings. However, in academic research, luxury goods become the main interest, especially high-end fashion items (Li et al., 2020; Urumutta Hewage et al., 2021; McCollough, 2020). Overall, research on conspicuous consumption in the fashion industry provides insights into the complex interplay between individual identity, social dynamics, and consumer culture in shaping fashion preferences and consumption behaviors. Conspicuous signaling behavior is the main activity carried out by luxury goods users, and this results in more engagement due to increased satisfaction for the user (Mahendra, 2023). In turn, satisfaction with the impact of this signaling behavior will make someone consume the product again because of the increasing social status.

In recent days, the new phenomenon is growing into technology and gadgets, and health/wellness. Some researchers are exploring how individuals use health-related consumption to signal social status, cultural capital, or adherence to specific lifestyle ideals. This can include purchasing organic foods, superfoods, specialty supplements, or subscribing to particular diets or wellness trends. Additionally, as the market for functional foods and health products continues to grow, there is likely to be more research exploring the interplay between conspicuous consumption, health consciousness, and consumer behavior in this area.

While there might not be as much research specifically examining the relationship between conspicuous consumption and functional foods, there is increasing recognition of how consumption behaviors in the health and wellness industry can also serve as signals of status and identity. Research on conspicuous consumption in the context of functional foods may be relatively limited compared to other sectors, therefore this study aims to investigate how consumption behaviors in the functional foods industry contribute to status signaling and social identity. Research in this area is essential to develop to increase awareness and use of functional foods products.

The growth of the functional food industry has shown a positive trend in recent years. Based on data released by *statista.com* (2019), the global functional food industry market experienced an increase in revenue from 2017 of \$247.89 billion, increasing to \$319.93 billion in 2022. The Covid-19 pandemic has also significantly influenced the increase in functional food consumption in recent years. The fact is reinforced by several previous studies from Farzana et al. (2022), which state that functional food can reduce COVID-19 symptoms.

Functional foods are categorized as food ingredients that are harmless and serve to treat several diseases (Gautam et al., 2018), such as reducing the risk of osteoporosis, cancer, obesity, and cardiovascular problems, improving physical fitness and brain memory (Arnold et al., 2021; Sheikh et al., 2017; Izadi et al., 2018; Mikulec et al., 2022; Xiao et al., 2021; Munekata et al., 2021).

This research intends to fill the gap in the literature by developing a model of conspicuous consumption in the context of functional foods. Research question that will become the focus of this study is what factors play a role in conscious signaling and increasing a person's satisfaction, which will encourage him to continue consuming these functional foods products.

Are their motivations for continuously purchasing and consuming functional food influenced by social influence, health consciousness, attitude to functional food.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Theoretical foundations

When discussing conspicuous consumption in the context of functional foods, several theoretical frameworks from sociology, psychology, and marketing can be relevant. This study uses Veblen's Theory of Conspicuous Consumption and Theory of Planned behavior.

2.1.1 Veblen's theory of Conspicuous consumption

This theory, which originally focused on the consumption of luxury goods, can be extended to functional foods. Just as individuals use luxury items to signal social status and wealth, they may also use health-conscious consumption, such as purchasing organic or specialty foods, to signal their commitment to health and well-being. Conspicuous consumption behavior, which is usually carried out in the form of showing the luxury of an item, apparently also applies to functional foods (Phuong & Dat, 2017). These findings confirm that social factors, such as social status, can be a strong driver in motivating consumers to choose functional foods. Purchasing functional foods, as revealed in research by (Barauskaite et al. (2018), was influenced by social and hedonic motivations.

2.1.2 Theory of Planned Behaviour

In behavioral psychology research's scope, Theory of Planned Behavior (developed by Ajzen in 1991) emerged as a useful framework in explaining the making of human decisions and actions. This theory states that we can predict a person's behavior through their intentions, which are influenced by three main factors: attitude, subjective norms, and perceived behavior (Ajzen, 1991). Our study applies these three factors into certain variables: attitude is represented by the attitude toward functional food, subjective norms are represented by social influence, and perceived behavioral control is represented by the health consciousness. The main focus of our study is to understand why consumers repeat purchases which are based on conspicuous consumption behavior. The tendency for conspicuous consumption, which can be explained through the theory of planned behavior, has a positive relationship with the evaluation of the functional food category in terms of features and frequency of purchase. Not only on the basis of social and hedonic motivation, sociodemographic criteria also influence functional food consumption, as tried to be explained by Horská et al. (2023) where age, gender and education level can influence functional food consumption. For example, consumers with a university degree are more interested in consuming functional foods.

2.2. Model development

The conspicuous consumption model in relation to Functional Foods is built from the theory of planned behavior and conspicuous consumption theory, which involves various variables including: health consciousness, Social Influence, Attitude to Functional Foods, and Functional Foods Conspicuous Consumption.

2.2.1 Health Consciousness

Health consciousness refers to the degree to which a person cares about health and how health affects daily activities (Chen, 2011). Individuals with high health consciousness are reflected in their attention (awareness) in running a healthy lifestyle by implementing healthy behaviors, in this context, consuming functional food. (Huang et al., 2019). Functional food is a diet that focuses on health, where the types of food consumed are oriented towards nutritional balance, variety, and the level of mixture in the presentation. (Niva, 2006).

Health consciousness can determine how a person's behavior in everyday life includes behavior in consuming something. This fact can be seen in research on consumers in China, which states that health consciousness is used as the main reason for safe food consumption. (Liu et al., 2013). Health Consciousness, together with the food system, also has a significant influence on purchase intention in the eyes of consumers. (Huang et al., 2019). Research on health consciousness related to functional food has also been conducted by Barauskaite et al (2018), stating that someone who has high health consciousness will have a greater possibility of consuming functional food. Although several previous studies explain the relationship between health consciousness and purchase intention, there are still few studies that relate it to buying in the sense of conspicuous consumption, so this study proposes a hypothesis as follows:

H1: Health Consciousness has a positive and significant influence on Functional Food Conspicuous Consumption.

2.2.2 Social Influence

Social influence is one factor that plays an essential role in someone's decision to buy something (Roy et al. 2018). One of their findings states that social influence is an external factor that can stimulate customers to purchase something. When associated with motivations and associations, social influence moderates the purchasing behavior of a luxury item (Roy et al., 2018). Specifically, research conducted by (Higgs et al., 2019) explains how Social Influence affects eating behavior in food consumption.

This study examines the relationship/correlation between social influence and conspicuous consumption. Based on previous research (Bongazana, 2014), it is explained that social influence significantly influences conspicuous consumption by consumers in South Africa. This research further strengthens one of the research results (Veblen, 1899) that every consumer tries to maintain his individual and social image repeatedly and consistently. This study explains that Social Influence is an essential factor in Conspicuous Consumption behavior in consumers. Social influence also causes a change in attitude towards a person in making a decision (Cham et al., 2022). In the scope of online shopping, research Hu et al. (2019) concluded that social influence positively influence on attitudes toward online shopping. Likewise, it also happens to a product brand Otterbring (2021), in his research results, states that social influence can change a person's attitude towards a brand, which can even lead to switching intentions.

Based on the above explanation, a hypothesis can be made as follows:

H2: Social Influence has a significant influence on conspicuous consumption behavior.

H3: Social Influence has a significant influence on attitude to functional Foods.

2.2.3 Attitude to Functional Foods

Attitude refers to pleasant and unpleasant evaluations of intentions and behavior (Ajzen, 1991). Attitude is a belief in something; more benefits are obtained when choosing or buying a particular product (Fanandaru et al., 2023; Khan et al., 2023). The research aligns with the potential benefits and risks aspects which are the primary considerations for consumers in buying a product, especially in purchasing functional food (Quan et al., 2020). In other studies conducted, it was also noted that the determinants of purchase intention are attitude and hedonic attitude. Hedonic attitude is an evaluation process related to emotional satisfaction and experiences involving the senses in humans (Qi & Ploeger, 2021).

Based on this literature, attitude towards functional food and hedonic attitude determine each individual to buy something. This research explores whether attitude to functional food positively influences functional food conspicuous consumption, so a hypothesis can be formulated as follows.

H4: Attitude to functional foods has a positive and significant influence on Functional Food Conspicuous Consumption

2.2.4 Functional Foods Conspicuous Consumption

Thorstein Veblen (1899) stated that conspicuous consumption is a way to make luxury goods as a symbol of well-being for a person, especially in one's financial condition, so the concept of conspicuous consumption is closely related to luxury goods (Huang & Wang, 2018). following the literature development Bagwell & Bernheim (1996) describe conspicuous consumption as a person's willingness to pay more to show the level of wealth, social status, social values, and representation of the chosen identity (Johnson et al., 2018). Research related to conspicuous consumption will also develop and focus on something other than luxury goods. Conspicuous consumption is also used in pro-social products such as reusable grocery bags (Johnson et al., 2018), green products (Policarpo et al., 2022), and functional food (Barauskaite et al., 2018).

In general, the decision to engage in conspicuous consumption is formed not only based on material needs that the product can meet but also on social values such as prestige. (Desmichel & Rucker, 2024). The social value emanating from the goods a person uses significantly impacts the individual's level of satisfaction, as found in a study by Brown & Gathergood (2017). The study states that the visible social value of one's consumption can contribute positively to one's level of satisfaction. Research by Ki and Kim (2016) confirmed that conspicuous consumption has a positive effect. Positive affect is defined as the positive emotions consumers feel as a result of their actions. (Clark et al., 2003).

The repurchase intention of a product is also influenced by conspicuous consumption behavior, as in research Lee et al. (2022), where someone who buys a shoe product by raffling tends to make a repurchase (repurchase intention). In his research, Melo et al. (2021) state that conspicuous consumption behavior will influence a person to repurchase the product by paying attention to the "guilt and pleasure" factor. So, this study formulates the following hypothesis:

H5: FF Conspicuous Consumption will positively influence Customer Satisfaction

H6: FF Conspicuous Consumption will positively influence Conspicuous Repurchase Intention

2.2.5 Customer Satisfaction to Conspicuous Repurchase Intention

Previous research shows that conspicuous repurchase intention and customer satisfaction are closely related. A study states that Pleasure and Guilty is a mediation that can positively impact and strengthen the relationship between Style Consumption, Conspicuous Consumption and Repurchase Intention. (Ki, 2017). In addition, Customer Satisfaction in the restaurant industry also has a vital role for consumers in revisiting intentions. (Cakici et al., 2019). Meanwhile, in the world of theme parks, a study conducted in Malaysia states that customer delight and satisfaction significantly influence customer loyalty, leading to revisiting intention (Ali et al., 2018). The research conducted by Kiranmayi (2019) clearly explains that customer satisfaction significantly influence on repurchase intention. This research was conducted on branded footwear consumers in India.

In several previous studies, repurchase intention was influenced by several factors or variables. The research conducted by Nguyen (2020) states that attitude is the most influential factor in repurchase intention behavior. The attitude consists of 5 things: consumer knowledge, environmental concern, personal norms, subjective norms, and health consciousness. Repurchase Intention that occurs in the world of hospitality also explains that perceived functional value, hedonic value, and symbolic/expressive value have a considerable role. (Peng & Chen, 2019). Meanwhile, research in 2022 on repurchase intention related to conspicuous consumption has been conducted by Lee et al., (2022), states that consumers who make purchases and participate in raffle marketing activities and have conspicuous consumption behavior tend to have a stronger repurchasing intention.

Thus, this study examines Conspicuous Consumption Repurchase Intention which refers to the desire to repurchase products that can increase emotional responses and provide intrinsic pleasure and satisfaction to show social status, wealth, prestige, and acceptance in the group (Lee et al., 2019). Therefore, the researcher proposes a hypothesis as follows:

H7: Customer satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on conspicuous repurchase intention.

Figure 1: Research Model

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Sample and Collection

This research uses quantitative methods where the variables to be tested consist of four independent variables and two dependent variables (Figure 1).

Data collected using an online survey, criteria for respondents involved in this study are: (1) individuals who in the last six months have consumed functional food. (2) Consumers who have made purchases of functional food at least two times (3) Age range 22 - 65 years (4) domiciled in the Greater Jakarta, Bogor, Depok, Tangerang, and Bekasi areas.

Before the questionnaire was distributed to the respondents, the researcher first conducted a pilot test on 30 respondents. Results from the pilot test show that all the items in the questionnaire were valid, reliable, and all items in the questionnaire were obvious and not multi-interpreted. In determining the sample this study used a judgmental sampling method, of the 333 responses collected, 309 responses were deemed to be fit for analysis (Table 1). Functional foods reported consumed by respondents in this study include yogurt, brown rice, milk, fruit extract, and probiotic drinks.

Table 1: Respondent profile

<i>Category</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
<i>Gender</i>		
Male	100	32,4%
Female	209	67,6%
<i>Age</i>		
18 – 25	249	80,6%
26 – 35	41	13,3%
36 – 45	15	4,9%
46 – 55	3	1,0%
> 65	1	0,3%
<i>Monthly Household Outcome</i>		
Less Than Rp 5.000.000,-	134	43,4%
Rp 5.000.000 - Rp 10.000.000	73	23,6%
Rp 10.000.000 - Rp 20.000.000	49	15,9%
Rp 20.000.000 - Rp 25.000.000	14	4,5%
More Than Rp 25.000.000	39	12,6%
<i>Education</i>		
High School	88	28,5%
D3 (Associate Degree)	19	6,1%
Undergraduate – Bachelor	177	57,3%
Master Graduate – Magister	25	8,1%
<i>Occupation</i>		
Student	157	50,8%
Civil Servant	46	14,9%
Employee	63	20,4%
Businessman	31	10,0%
Others	12	3,9%

Table.1 describes the composition of the respondents involved in this study. 67.6% of respondents are women and the remaining 32.4% are men, so this shows that gender representation has been well met. Similarly, the age of respondents where most are aged 18-25 years by 80.6% and this is in line with the occupation of respondents where most are students with a percentage of 50.8%. In addition, education also illustrates that the most composition is Undergraduate-Bachelor at 57.3% and high school at 28.5%, which is also in line with the age composition where the most is 18-25 years old. So, from this explanation, the composition of the respondents is sufficiently well represented.

3.2 Measures

For the number of samples used, this research has met the requirements where there are at least 10 times the number of respondents from all indicators. (Memon et al., 2020), there were 21 indicators used in this study so that the minimum number of respondents was 210 respondents, while in this study the number of valid respondents involved was 309 respondents. Item in questionnaire rated using five point Likert scale ranging from 1(strongly disagree) to 5(Strongly agree) (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016).

The questions contained in the questionnaire come from previous studies, where there are six variables to be studied, namely Functional Food Conspicuous Consumption where there are four questions. (Leelakasemsant et al., 2018), three questions related to Attitude to functional food (Al-Swidi et al., 2014), Social Influence which consists of four questions (Roy et al., 2018), repurchase intention (Lee et al., 2019) and customer satisfaction to functional food (Hussein, 2018) each has four questions, and the last one is Health Consciousness (Nagaraj, 2021) which consists of three questions. The detailed measurement items used in this study can be seen in Table.2:

Table 2: Measurement Item

Construct	Item
<i>Health Consciousness</i>	(HC1) I am very conscious of my health.
	(HC2) I am usually conscious of my health.
	(HC3) I am aware of my health condition as I go about my day.
<i>Social Influence</i>	(SI1) Before consuming functional food, it is important to know the type of functional food that will make me attractive to others.
	(SI2) Before consuming functional food, I know about the type of people who consume functional food.
	(SI3) I often pay attention to what type of functional food other people consume.
	(SI4) I always find out what kind of functional food can give me a positive impression of myself.
<i>Attitude to functional foods</i>	(ATTF1) I prefer functional food because it is processed without chemicals.
	(ATTF2) I prefer functional foods because they are more nutritious than conventional non-organic foods.
	(ATTF3) I prefer functional food because it is environmentally friendly.
<i>Functional foods Conspicuous Consumption</i>	(FFCC1) I buy functional food because it increases my popularity.
	(FFCC2) I buy functional food because it gets me noticed by others.
	(FFCC3) I buy functional food to show who I am.
	(FFCC4) By consuming functional food, I want to show something implicitly to others around me.
<i>Customer satisfaction</i>	(CS1) I feel satisfied with the decision to buy functional food products
	(CS2) I have a pleasant experience when consuming functional food
	(CS3) This functional food product meets my expectations
<i>Repurchase intention</i>	(RI1) I intend to continue to buy functional foods.
	(RI2) I intend to continue consuming functional food products.
	(RI3) I intend to continue to choose functional food as an option for my future consumption.
	(RI4) Unless there is an unforeseen reason, I intend to continue buying functional food.

Researchers used Partial Least Square (PLS) path modeling technique to test the hypotheses proposed in this study and SmartPLS 4.0 as an application that helps analyze the relationships that occur between variables. The PLS technique used in this study is very useful in estimating a complex model with a not too large amount of data. In addition, PLS SEM is also a tool with minimal restrictions on measurement scales. (Chang et al., 2016).

4. RESULT

4.1 Outer Model

In testing the outer model in this study, there are three aspects that can be used to evaluate the quality of this research, the first is convergent validity, the second is discriminant validity, and the third is reliability. For convergent validity, the two criteria that must be considered are factor loading with a minimum value of 0.7 and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) with a minimum value of 0.5. For discriminant validity, you can see that the cross loading construc's square value is greater than other variables. Finally, for reliability, it can be seen from the composite reliability value where the value is greater than > 0.7 (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016).

Table 3: Convergent Validity

	<i>Attitude to Functional Food</i>	<i>Customer Satisfaction</i>	<i>Functional Food Conspicuous Consumption</i>	<i>Health Consciousness</i>	<i>Repurchase Intention</i>	<i>Social Influence</i>
ATTF1	0,787					
ATTF2	0,835					
ATTF3	0,683					
CS1		0,902				
CS2		0,881				
CS3		0,898				
FFCC1			0,829			
FFCC2			0,910			
FFCC3			0,909			
FFCC4			0,834			
HC1				0,968		
HC2				0,853		
HC3				0,669		
RI1					0,885	
RI2					0,904	
RI3					0,855	
RI4					0,737	
SI1						0,823
SI2						0,703
SI3						0,720
SI4						0,805
SI5						0,753

Based on Table.3, it can be seen that the results of the convergent validity analysis in this study can be declared valid. There are several indicators whose values are still below 0.7 (ATTF3 and HC3) but none have a value of less than 0.5. The value limit greater than 0.5 in convergent validity is still acceptable. (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016) but with some notes such as validity and reliability that must meet the requirements.

Table 4: Discriminant Validity

	ATTF	CS	FFCC	HC	RI	SI
Attitude to Functional Food						
Customer Satisfaction	0,664					
Functional Food Conspicuous Consumption	0,530	0,085				
Health Consciousness	0,541	0,399	0,111			
Repurchase Intention	0,775	0,776	0,138	0,455		
Social Influence	0,582	0,234	0,746	0,239	0,242	

To test the discriminant validity of the results of this study, researchers used the Heterotrait-monotrait ratio (HTMT) method. (Henseler et al., 2015). The results of the discriminant validity test (table.4) show that all variables involved have a value below 0.9. Which means it has good convergent consistency and can be distinguished between constructs.

Table 5: Reliability

	Cronbach's alpha	AVE
ATTF	0.714	0.528
CS	0.875	0.799
FFCC	0.894	0.759
HC	0.837	0.703
RI	0.868	0.719
SI	0.819	0.581

The reliability test carried out in this study is to use Cronbach's alpha and AVE (average variance extracted) values. Based on the results of the reliability test in this study (table.5), all variables are declared reliable because the value of each construct has a Cronbach alpha greater than 0.7 ($\alpha > 0.7$) and an AVE with a value above 0.5 ($AVE > 0.5$).

4.2 Inner Model

For the Inner Model, researchers used two tests, namely the R-Square test and the p-value hypothesis test. (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). Table.6 explains that of the seven hypotheses proposed, three hypotheses were rejected with a p-value above 0.05 (H3, H5, and H6). While the remaining four hypotheses are accepted with a p-value below 0.05. For R-square in this study, there are two variables that fall into the medium category, namely Functional Food Conspicuous Consumption (0.467) and Repurchase Intention (0.478), while the other two variables fall into the weak category, namely Attitude to Functional Food and Customer Satisfaction.

Table 6: Path coefficient

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	Original Sample (O)	
Health Consciousness -> Functional Food Conspicuous Consumption (H1)	-0,080	-0,063	0,052	1,548	0,149	Rejected
Social Influence -> Functional Food Conspicuous Consumption (H2)	0,525	0,525	0,046	11,434	0,000	Accepted
Social Influence -> Attitude to Functional Food (H3)	0,475	0,480	0,053	8,963	0,000	Accepted
Attitude to Functional Food -> Functional Food Conspicuous Consumption (H4)	0,247	0,241	0,067	3,688	0,001	Accepted
Functional Food Conspicuous Consumption -> Customer Satisfaction (H5)	0,081	0,083	0,072	1,128	0,254	Rejected
Functional Food Conspicuous Consumption -> Repurchase Intention (H6)	0,078	0,074	0,048	1,644	0,118	Rejected
Customer Satisfaction -> Repurchase Intention (H7)	0,681	0,688	0,045	15,258	0,000	Accepted

Figure 2: Path Coefficient

5. DISCUSSION

This study found several interesting findings that help shed light on conspicuous consumption study that is still rare, especially in functional foods. The results of this study confirm that it turns out that conspicuous consumption behavior is not only for goods that are tangible and luxurious but can also be seen in the consumption of food that is not necessarily expensive but has the same psychological impact, namely the perception of the social status of the user.

Results show that of seven hypotheses tested, four ideas were proven, namely the relationship between social influence on conspicuous consumption of functional food (H2), attitude to functional food on conspicuous consumption of functional food (H4), social impact on attitude to functional food (H3), and Customer Satisfaction on Repurchase Intention (H7). The results of this study show that social influence has a positive influence on functional food conspicuous consumption. These results are consistent with what was found in Roy et al. (2018) research, which stated that social influence is an external factor that can encourage people to buy something. Especially for purchasing luxury fashion goods, social influence positively influences purchase and repurchase (Xia et al., 2022; Song et al., 2022). This finding also aligns with the theory of conspicuous consumption explained by Veblen (1899), which states that every consumer always tries to maintain their individual and social image repeatedly and consistently, especially when purchasing luxury goods such as fashion.

Apart from influencing conspicuous consumption, the results of this study also show that social influence significantly influences attitudes toward functional food. This was explained by Barauskaite et al. (2018), who stated that someone who wants to be seen as having a healthy lifestyle prefers functional food. These results are also consistent with the study conducted by Iyer et al. 2022 where social influence has a role in a person's attitude toward authentic products. This study proves that attitude toward functional foods significantly influences conspicuous consumption. From some existing literature, the results of this study can be clearly explained, such as Küster-Boluda & Vidal-Capilla (2017), which state that attitude toward functional foods directly influences willingness to consume. In another study that discusses consumer behavior in Vietnam in consuming yogurt as one of the functional foods, the researchers found that the attitude toward functional foods directly affects willingness to consume. Nguyen et al. (2019) explain that attitude to functional food significantly influences purchase intention.

Customer satisfaction was found to have a significant effect on repurchase intention. Some previous studies, such as Bhutto et al. (2023), explain that customer satisfaction will increase the level of trust and expectations of a person towards a product so that there is no doubt in making repurchase intention. Kiranmayi (2019) also explains how the customer satisfaction relationship directly influences repurchase intention behavior, where the most influential thing in satisfaction is the impact felt on a person when consuming a product. The effect of customer satisfaction on repurchase intention on organic food is also discussed in research by Bhutto et al. (2023), where brand awareness affects customer satisfaction, which will encourage someone to repurchase intention. Some of these studies' research results on the relationship between Customer Satisfaction and Repurchase Intention align with previous studies.

In contrast to what had been hypothesized, health consciousness did not influence functional food consumption. The result is surprising because other studies show that health consciousness influences functional food consumption (Kapoor & Munjal, 2017). One possibility is that not all respondents are aware of the potential of functional food to improve social status and only see that based on functional value (Desmichel & Rucker, 2024).

Results from this study show that the behavior of functional food consumption does not significantly affect customer satisfaction. Previous research by Charoennan & Huang (2018) mentioned that purchases that lead to customer satisfaction mostly come from conspicuous consumption behavior. In contrast, in the study, the object used was luxury fashion products. In that case, an explanation can be given that conspicuous consumption behavior in functional food differs from that in luxury fashion products, especially in customer satisfaction after purchasing a product. This also raises the possibility that there are other things besides customer satisfaction as a follow-up effect after conspicuous consumption of functional food, such as consumer pleasure (Alnsour et al., 2018), symbolic status (Sahin & Nasir, 2022), happiness (Charoennan & Huang, 2018) and perceived elevated status (Kumar et al., 2022)

Other results from this study show that functional food conspicuous consumption behavior does not directly influence repurchase intention behavior. These results contrast with the study of Hamdani et al. (2023), who found conspicuous consumption in fashion to repurchase; however, previous studies in functional food have not found a direct relationship between conspicuous consumption and repurchase intention. This shows that the relationship between conspicuous consumption and repurchase intention in functional food is mediated by other factors, such as consumer pleasure (Ki et al., 2017) and guilt (Alnsour et al., 2018).

6. CONCLUSION

The results of this study add to the repertoire of science, especially those related to functional food and conspicuous consumption, so that it underlies a person's repurchase intention. Of the seven hypotheses proposed in this study, four hypotheses are accepted, where it can be concluded that Social Influence has a vital role in the behavior of functional food conspicuous consumption compared to the health consciousness factor. This is in line with the central concept of conspicuous consumption theory. Veblen (1989) which states that conspicuous consumption is a purchase that aims one of them is prestige. This is in line with the results of the research that has been described that functional food consumed by a person can increase prestige in a person and create an image as if living a healthy lifestyle.

From this research, several insights and new findings can be applied to business actors or practitioners, especially those related to functional food products, and conspicuous consumption behavior from the consumer's point of view. First, this study shows that Social Influence has strongly influenced consumers in determining whether to consume functional food products, especially in matters related to conspicuous consumption. Companies will be helped by this research, especially if they want to create a campaign to introduce a functional food product to consumers. The campaign launched must contain social contexts that significantly affect functional food conspicuous consumption behavior as in this study.

Second, health consciousness has a minor role in influencing consumer behavior in consuming functional food, especially conspicuous consumption behavior. In making a campaign for consumers, companies can prioritize health consciousness to their target market rather than just everything related to social influence.

Third, so that consumers carry out repurchase intention behavior towards a functional food product consumer satisfaction must be considered. However, the findings of this study state that functional food conspicuous consumption behavior does not significantly affect customer satisfaction. So, it is necessary to re-examine what other factors cause customer satisfaction to be high in the functional food industry so that it causes repurchase intention as expected.

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